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Abstract

This thesis discusses gender inequity across twelve diverse countries, including Niger, Haiti, the Central African Republic, India, Afghanistan, Ecuador, Guatemala, China, the United States, Canada, the Netherlands, and Finland. The research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of gender disparities by examining socio-cultural, economic, and political factors within various countries, emphasizing the importance of addressing gender disparities and promoting inclusivity globally.

The thesis is organized into the following sections. First, a review of the literature provides context to the topic of gender inequity in education. This is followed by a discussion and overview of various sociological theories that contribute to our understanding of this subject matter. The third section explains the methodology designed to conduct the study. Subsequently, the results are presented, categorized by country. A thematic discussion of the findings follows to enhance our understanding of their importance. Finally, the thesis concludes with a discussion on the significance of the results and a call to action.

The findings reveal varying degrees of gender inequity, with disparities evident in educational opportunities, workforce participation, political representation, and health outcomes. Common themes of gender inequity emerge across the countries, with socio-cultural barriers playing a significant role. Patriarchal attitudes, limited roles for women, and traditional views on gender roles contribute to early marriages, restricted autonomy, and gender-based violence. A call to action is presented to ensure that every girl and woman around the world has the opportunity and ability to reach their full academic potential.

Keywords: gender inequity, education, economic constraints, quality of education, women's empowerment, sociological theory, educational access, literacy rates, country development

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Introduction

Education is a fundamental right. Education is crucial to the development of individuals, communities, countries, and the overall society. As of 2023, there are over 130 million school-aged girls that are denied the essential human right to education (United Nations, 2023). As the famous old African proverb states, “If you educate a man, you educate an individual, but if you educate a woman, you educate a family (nation)” (Suen, 2013, p.61). The purpose of this thesis is to illustrate the problem of gender inequity in education worldwide.

This thesis explores the argument that the level of schooling people have, specifically women’s ability to access education, is one of the main determinants in the development of a country. Gender inequity persists in education around the world and is continuing to be a global issue. This thesis focuses on highlighting the various challenges that girls and women face in education and presents strategies to combat this critical issue. Gender inequity is identified as a major challenge in the literature exploring access to education (Unterhailer, 2022). It is important to note that gender inequality and gender inequity are different. In this context, I refer to gender inequity as providing more resources to those most in need, opposed to gender inequality which is the application of providing the same resources to everyone across the globe. In this thesis, I recognize the cultural differences various countries face and understand that people around the world need different solutions.

There are massive benefits when countries around the world educate women. When women are better educated, they are more informed about nutrition, are knowledgeable about healthcare, have fewer children, marry at a later age, have a healthier family, and are more likely to join the formal labor market (World Bank, 2022). Humans are simultaneously individuals, members of families, and members of groups (Bitz, 2023, p.66) As individuals possess this tri-

nature, they assume various roles and responsibilities. When women and girls are provided with the opportunity to receive proper education, they exemplify the interconnected nature of individual, familial, and societal aspects of human life, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The Benefit of Women's Education Based on Three Levels

Individual Level	Familial Level	Community/ Country (Group) Level
Women's earnings increase 10% from each additional year of schooling	Children born from a literate mother are 50% more likely to live past five years old	Investing in girl's education contributes to the nation's economic growth which boosts their GDP by ~35% with each additional year of schooling
Girls who have completed secondary schooling are six times less likely to be married as children	Educating women establish mentally strong, physically active, well nourished, proactive, and productive families	Educating women contributes to the desire and ability to become contributors to technological advancement, which in turns increases national development

Access to education is a crucial element in promoting women's empowerment and aids in the opportunity to have skills, knowledge, and confidence to participate in society and the improvement of their lives (Reshi et al., 2022). Educating girls and women can be seen as one of the best investments in international development (Evans et al., 2023). Millions of girls and women around the world face barriers to education. This comprehensive review explores the challenges faced by women in accessing education in various countries, including Niger, Haiti, the Central African Republic, India, Afghanistan, Ecuador, Guatemala, China, the United States, Canada, the Netherlands, and Finland.

When selecting countries for my research, I made sure to include diverse continents and regions, along with countries representing various levels of economic development. Particularly, Niger, Haiti, Central African Republic, and Afghanistan fall under the category of least

developed countries, while India, Ecuador, China, and Guatemala are considered developing countries. On the other hand, the United States, Canada, The Netherlands, and Finland are classified as developed countries. Additionally, my selection was influenced by my existing knowledge and comfort with these countries, ensuring a more informed and nuanced exploration of the complex issues surrounding gender disparities in education.

This thesis is organized into the following sections. First, I review the literature providing context to the topic of gender inequity in education. This is followed by a discussion and overview of various sociological theories that are helpful in our understanding of this subject matter. The third section of this thesis explains the methodology I designed to conduct the study. This is followed by the results I found, categorized by country. Next, a thematic discussion of the findings helps us understand their importance. Finally, I conclude with a call to action to ensure that every girl and woman around the world has the opportunity and ability to reach their full academic potential.

Literature Review

This comprehensive literature review focuses on the persistent issue of gender inequity in education worldwide. Factors such as poverty, societal discrimination, and the lack of educational infrastructure contribute to these disparities, perpetuating a cycle that disproportionately affect girls and women's education. The recent challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic have further emphasized the urgent need for equitable access to education. This review emphasizes the urgent necessity of removing systemic barriers and creating an enabling environment for the education and empowerment of girls and women worldwide.

For the past several decades, the differences in education among boys and girls have been the center of scientific attention (Crispina, et al., 2020). In 2007, the Global Education

Monitoring Report emphasized the significance of addressing gender inequity to foster sustainable development and enhance global growth. Later in 2013, the United Nations further recognized that importance and created the *Sustainable Development Goals* which declares that every person worldwide is entitled to have an education, and more specifically focuses on decreasing poverty, empowering women in education in the workplace, reducing infant mortality, and improving health institutions throughout the world. (Somani, 2017)

In 2022, two thirds of all global illiterate adults (773 million) were women (Courtney, 2022). The *Global Feminization of Poverty* refers to women worldwide who are disproportionately living in poverty, without access to sufficient healthcare, food, water, housing. It also refers to women in developing nations who are often times denied fundamental/ civil rights, access to education, and forbidden the usage and acquiring of money. (Courtney, 2022) In regard to developed countries, discrimination is about working life. Whereas in developing countries, discrimination is often found in daily and basic areas of life such as violence against women and women's unequal access to education. (Kandemir, 2022, p. 821)

For many education systems in both developed and developing countries who do not have a universal education system, poverty is one the biggest contributors of widening gender education gaps (Kandemir, 2022, p. 825). Poverty has such a detrimental impact on children's education. Young children who grow up in poverty face disproportionate challenges compared to children who grow up in higher income backgrounds such as cognitive and literary ability. The National Center for Education Statistic found that these disproportionate challenges on young children begin in kindergarten and continue to be a challenge throughout elementary and high school. (Crispina et al., 2020, p. 891).

People living in poverty are attributed with the majority of the gender gaps in primary school enrollment. This pattern can be described through horizontal vs vertical convergence. The horizontal convergence describes that the process of all socioeconomic groups are simultaneously experiencing narrowing gender gaps in education. On the other hand, vertical convergence describes the process of wealthier socioeconomic groups experience the narrowing gender gaps first and the poorest girls and women are the last to experience this process (Psaki et al., 2020, p. 135)

Ragnar Nurske, an economist, introduced a circle model representing the vicious cycle of poverty, represented in Figure 1. The issue of underdevelopment has led to the widespread usage of this model. The usage of this cycle, in relation to countries, is important because this model represents that “underdeveloped countries are poor because they are poor.” It also represents the vicious circle of education starting with low income (people in poverty who are not in school), to insufficient spending on education systems and vocational training, which leads to low productivity, finally leading back to low income. (Kandemir, 2022, p. 825). This cycle disproportionately affects women in underdeveloped countries.

Figure 1. Nurke’s Vicious Cycle of Poverty

However, poverty is not the only contributor to the problem of gender inequity in schooling. Some of the other factors include geographic remoteness, lack of school infrastructure, and the discrimination of girls and women in society (Crispina et al., 2020, p. 892). With the increase in population, there have become rapid increases in enrollment which contribute to overcrowded classrooms and shortage of materials (Psaki et al., 2020, p. 135). When these issues arise, girls and young women are often the first to be excluded or denied access to education. Furthermore, girls face additional challenges than boys such as early marriage and pregnancy that result in them having to leave school (Psaki et al., 2020, p. 119).

Girls are influenced by their parents and social institutions, consistently receiving messages that affect their self-perception and shape their roles in society and career choices (Courtney, 2022). In many schools around the world, it is often found that textbooks lack positive role models for girls, and that boys dominate the classroom (Crispina et al., 2020, p. 890). This leaves girls feeling secluded and discriminated against which contributes to their leave.

The pandemic impacted the entire education system. For many developed countries, the transition to online distance education was almost seamless. However, for many low-income parts in the world and developing countries, it was not that easy (Abulikemu, 2023, p.21). The pandemic led to adverse situations for students, families, and faculty members. The people who suffered the most from the pandemic were students who came from poor families with low education levels and children with poor learning motivation (Tadesse & Muluye, 2020). Some places were not able to provide distance learning because of economic and technological difficulties. The pandemic has exposed how crises are endured in local settings. This emphasized

the that challenges of measurement of gender inequality in education are conceptual and operational which require certain collaborations (Unterhalter et al., 2022, p. 521).

Gender parity has been the primary metric for assessing gender inequality in education for approximately three decades (Unterhalter et al., 2022, p. 513). From the pandemic, the gender parity measurement has been seen to be problematic. The measurement has a limited presumption of what gender is and debates on how to define gender, it presents a poor connection between education systems with other social relations, and it proposes that gender can be something constant (Unterhalter et al., 2022, p. 519).

Providing young girls and women with access to high-quality education without gender stereotyping and obstacles is one of the most significant global priorities, because girls and women around the world are limited in regard to their natural talents and interests which contributes to the limitation and restriction of economic progress and social cohesion (Crispina et al., 2020, p. 890).

Theoretical Framework

Feminist Theory, Conflict Theory, Symbolic Interactionism, Social Reproduction Theory, Functionalism Theory, Bourdieu's Theory of Cultural Capital, and Intersectional Theory are all important when researching gender inequity in education around the world because they provide different lenses through which one can analyze the complexities of this issue. Each theory offers a unique perspective and set of tools to examine the multifaceted nature of gender disparities in education.

Feminist Theory

As women and young girls around the world are faced with limited opportunities to receive an education, it hinders their ability to achieve complete equal rights. Feminist theories

focus on the conditions that shape a woman's life and refuse to accept that inequity between genders is unavoidable (Jackson & Jones, 1998, p. 1). This theory is strongly correlated to inequity between men and women in education because feminism has continuously fought for women's right to access quality education (Alhumaid, 2019, p.34). The education system reflects gender inequity and creates inequity in society.

Regarding education, feminist theories focus on the unequal achievements of girls and women and the hidden agendas of various policies and practices concerning education (Dikshit, 2022, p.34). There are multiple feminist theories, but this section examines the "Big Three" of feminist thought including, liberal feminism, Marxist/ social feminism, and radical feminism. Despite analyzing three different forms of feminism, they all have something in common, they all focus on assessing the disparities between genders within society.

The liberal feminist perspective advocates for equal opportunities and removing discrimination within education (Shukla, 2019, p. 56). Theorists, under this approach, support women achieving their full potential in all areas of their lives, including personal freedom and autonomy. Liberal feminists recommend equitable access through the enforcement of legislation, policies, and changes in socialization practices. Liberal feminists argue that schools have failed women in relation to their education, family, and occupation because of the traditional mindset that is instilled upon them at a young age (Dikshit, 2022, p.28). Liberal feminists demand access to education for all and believe that through education, women can achieve higher social and political roles (Dikshit, 2022, p.26).

The radical feminist perspective on education focuses on the male dominance of knowledge and culture (Shukla, 2019, p. 56). They argue that education is a patriarchal institution that oppresses women and girls, as well as reinforces power dynamics that benefit

men. Theorists under this approach believe that women and girls are taught from a young age to work a triple burden shift. The concept, triple burden shift, was coined by Duncombe and Marsden in 1995, and found that women are expected to perform housework, paid work, and emotional work. Women have been constantly ignored when making higher decisions and contributions. Men have silenced men perpetuating the fact that they are the ones in dominant and powerful positions when making rules (Dikshit, 2022, p.29). Radical feminists advocate for educational restructuring through the reformation of school curriculum, inclusive policies, and fostering inclusivity.

The Marxist/ socialist perspective on education believes that schooling is mutually dependent on the class structure and the economic system of capital determines a woman's education (Dikshit, 2022, p.30). Theorists under this approach also believe that capitalism and patriarchy are connected and reinforce one another. Marxists believe that education reproduces class inequities. They believe the schooling system prepares the children of the bourgeoisie, the capitalist ruling class, for positions of power and authority. While the children of the proletariat, the working class, are being prepared for an education that keeps them in the working class, while simultaneously serving the interest of the ruling class.

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory was developed by Karl Marx as a critique of capitalism in the 19th century (Main, 2023). This theory asserted that people are in a state of conflict because they are in a competition for limited resources. It placed an emphasis on economic resources, power, and status. In regard to gender, conflict theory explains the social problems that occur when dominant groups, in this case men, mistreat subordinate groups, women, which creates an

unequal balance between genders. This theory argues, in relation to gender, that men attempt, and have been successful, to maintain this power and privilege over women.

Marx believed that capitalism created a class struggle, he highlighted the issue by analyzing between the bourgeoisie, the capitalist ruling class, and the proletariat, the working class. He found that the bourgeoisie, the owners of the means of production, exploited the proletariat for their labor (Main, 2023). Frederich Engels compared the family structure to Marx's idea of the bourgeoisie and proletariat. Engels found that the relationship of the family is very similar to Marx's original idea. He believed that the reason women had less power than men in the household is because the women were dependent on the men for wages. This suggests that when women are able to get an education and become wage earners, they gain a higher power in the family dynamic.

The conflict theory of education focuses on how conflict and inequity function in educational settings and through educational policies. The students who are more socioeconomically fortunate most often time receive better schooling and complete schooling with fewer obstacles compared to students who are not as socioeconomically fortunate (Ferrare et al., 2023, p. 591). Marxists conflict theorists believe that education is a means of perpetuating conflict, exploitation, and alienation. They also believe that education is a means of reinforcing hierarchical class (bourgeoisie and proletariat) through class relations and culture (Ferrare et al., 2023, p. 592).

Another way conflict theorists look at the inequity of education is the usage of standardized testing, the "hidden curriculum," and tracking. Children from lower-income families might not have access to the necessary books or technology. Critics of standardized testing claim that the questions are most likely to be known by white, middle-class students, and

that the scores of these tests represent students' socioeconomic status (Baligar, 2018). Conflict theorists also believe that there is a "hidden curriculum" which is a set of values and beliefs that preserve the social and economic hierarchy.

Lastly, tracking is an educational system in which administrators and teachers separate children into different groups, usually by their perceived academic ability. They put them into different programs or classrooms such as the "gifted student program" and "learning recovery program." These labels increase educational disparities and may cause students to behave according to these labels during their time at school or even for the rest of their lives (Ferrare et al., 2023, p.591).

Symbolic Interactionism

Symbolic interactionism is a theoretical perspective that observes how people interact and addresses the subjective meanings people put on objects. Our social interactions are based on our interpretation of the world rather than objective reality (Cole, 2017). Sociologists refer to our interactions of the world as subjective meanings. Blumer outlined basic tenets of symbolic interactionism, including (1) individuals act based on the meaning objects have for them, (2) interaction occurs within a particular social and cultural context in which physical objects, social objects, and situations are categorized by individual meanings, (3) meanings emerge from interactions with other individuals and society overall, and (4) meanings are continuously created and recreated during interactions with others (Carter & Fuller, 2016, p.932).

The concept of "doing gender" coined by West and Zimmerman highlights how masculinity and femininity are socially constructed, emerging from recurring, structured interactions, and processes of socialization. (Carter & Fuller, 2016, p.941). Educational facilities, like classrooms, are social environments where children develop an understanding about who

they are. Their beliefs, motivation, and performance can be majorly impacted because of the stereotypes given from school and surrounding classmates (Muntoni et al., 2021 p. 189).

Textbooks can be interpreted through the lens of a symbolic interactionist, as they serve as a means of communication between educators and students. Students use textbooks and interpret and make meaning behind the context of the books and create images of themselves from textbooks. Textbooks perpetuate stereotypes by associating characteristics with specific groups. Textbooks give knowledge while representing gender norms, which can shape the role in how children view themselves. In many countries, girls and women are underrepresented in textbooks. However, when they are included, they are shown in “traditional roles,” such as mothers, caregivers, daughters, and sisters (GEM Report, 2020).

Social Reproduction Theory

Social reproduction theory is the theoretical perspective of the reproduction of social inequalities through generations (Guo et al., 2021, p. 2566). Pierre Bourdieu analyzed the role of schools in the perpetuation of dominant culture, and he used social capital to define three different forms of capital including economic, symbolic, and cultural (Serna and Woulfe, 2017, p.2). Social reproduction theory identifies schools as a way to converse the dominant class’s ideologies, values, and powers (Serna and Woulfe, 2017, p.1).

This theory argues that schools are not institutions for equal opportunity. Instead, they are mechanisms for facilitating and perpetuating social inequalities. Educational facilities provide unequal resources and give students disproportionate opportunities based on their social capital (Guo et al., 2021, p. 2567). Under this theory schooling is a perpetuator of class division and power hierarchies created by a capitalistic culture with the purpose of maintaining the values of the wealth-based society (Serna & Woulfe, 2017, p.2). These factors lead to different educational

outcomes among social classes, ultimately contributing to the continuation of the generational socioeconomic status.

Functionalism Theory

Functionalism is a system of thinking based off of the ideas of sociologist Emile Durkheim, which looks at how all aspects of society, such as institution, roles, norms serve a purpose for the long-term survival of the society. In other words, the roles and institutions within a society are essential to the function of society. Durkheim believed that educational institutions reflect the needs, customs, and beliefs of the society providing it (Nickerson, 2023). He claimed that the function education serves are to instill societies values and socialize children. On the other hand, Shultz, another sociologist, viewed education as an investment people made on themselves to gain access to higher paying jobs.

Schools have two forms of functions, including manifest functions and latent functions. Manifest functions are the intended functions of society, and latent functions are the hidden or unintentional functions. Some examples of manifest functions of educational systems include socialization, social control, and cultural transmission. On the other hand, some examples of latent functions of educational systems include social networks, the creation of generational gaps, and political and social integration. Both of these forms of functions are preparing students for their future roles and functions within society.

Functionalists believe that gender disparities exist as a way to create a division of labor that perpetuate traditional gender roles, such as women are responsible for the domestic duties whereas men are responsible for providing finances for the family. The education system reinforces these traditional gender roles by the way they prepare children for society and instilling cultural norms and beliefs. Education has a positive effect on the belongingness to a

society, neighborhood, school, and family through the indicators such as the student's educational level, academic achievement, grade-weighted academic achievement, and the educational level of their parents (Chueng et al., 2016, p.228). When girls and women are given the ability to access high quality education, they are given the opportunity to a higher sense of belongingness therefore functioning in a society in a much bigger role.

Bourdieu's Theory of Cultural Capital

Cultural capital theory, developed by Pierre Bourdieu, is one way to explain how power in society is transferred and social classes are maintained. This theory focuses on the cultural aspects of social inequity, and how social mechanisms perpetuate the continuation of classes between generations (Košutić, 2017, p. 152). Capital are the assets people have whereas cultural capital are the knowledge, skills, values, and norms that are attained by being in a specific socioeconomic class.

Cultural capital is still a form of capital that can be, through education, transformed into economic capital (Košutić, 2017, p. 153). This theory can offer insight as to why some children are more academically successful compared to others. Bourdieu gives generational insight and argues that families with a high socioeconomic status transmit cultural capital to their children, and the children convert the cultural capital into educational and socioeconomical success (Jæger & Karlson, 2018, p. 775).

This theoretical concept is closely related to educational inequities because educational systems are one of the biggest contributors to legitimizing existing socioeconomic classes because they are based on the standards and knowledge of the upper class (Košutić, 2017, p. 152). According to Bourdieu, cultural capital exists in three states including embodied (e.g.,

language and mannerisms), objectified (e.g., cultural goods and books), and institutionalized (e.g., educational credentials) (Jæger & Møllegaard, 2017 p.133).

Bourdieu argued that each class had its own cultural framework in understanding the world which he refers to as habitus. This cultural framework includes different systems of thought, reasoning, and thinking for different family class positions (Košutić, 2017, p. 153). Many middle- and upper-class children are exposed to vastly different things compared to working class children which gives them skills and knowledge that advances their academic success.

Intersectional Theory

To tie in all of these theories, intersectionality is the theoretical study that social identities such as gender, race, class, ability, sexual orientation, age, religion, and nationality overlap and intersect with one another often simultaneously. Intersectionality, developed by Crenshaw (1989) argues that people are disadvantaged by multiple sources of oppression. These approaches are important when explaining educational inequities because it improves the understanding that individual experiences are related to interconnected systems of power, privilege, and oppression (Keller et al., 2023, p.30).

Leave no one behind is the foundation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Under LNOB, the United Nations understand that discrimination and inequalities are often multiple and intersect. The UN states:

“Many of the barriers people face in accessing services, resources and equal opportunities are not simply accidents of fate or a lack of availability of resources, but rather the result of discriminatory laws, policies and social practices that leave particular groups of people further and further behind” (UNSDG, 2022).

From an intersectional lens, educational inequities result from multidimensional disparities that uniquely and inequitably affect marginalized individuals. Acknowledging and understanding that people face intersecting forms of discrimination, educators and policy makers can better respond to the unique needs of the students.

Methodology

Selection Process

A comprehensive search was conducted using electronic databases including Google Scholar, Our World in Data, Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS), The World Bank Assessment Reports, UNICEF, Research Gate, and other various international sources to ensure a true global perspective using keywords such as “educational inequity,” “importance of educating girls,” “gender inequities in education,” “gender disparities in accessing education,” and “gender inequity and educational attainment.” The search was limited to articles and websites published between 2017 and 2023. However, quantitative data from as early as 1950 was used to present long-term trends. During the search process, the same keywords were utilized. However, the search was further refined by incorporating the names of specific countries along with the search terms to facilitate a more detailed analysis of the educational disparities within those countries.

Sociological Theories

I chose to use sociological theories to explain different perspectives to why gender inequity in education is a reoccurring problem. Additionally, it helped to further analyze my data to better understand the issue through the lens of a sociologist. There were specific sociological theories that were the most relevant and helpful. Feminist theory and Bourdieu's theory of

cultural capital emerged as the most applicable frameworks for analyzing gender inequity in education.

Feminist theory, with its focus on understanding and challenging gender-based inequalities, provided a comprehensive lens to examine the power dynamics and societal structures that contribute to educational disparities between genders. It emphasized the importance of considering how cultural, social, and economic factors intersect to shape educational experiences and opportunities for women and girls.

Complementing feminist theory, Bourdieu's theory of cultural capital added depth to the analysis by highlighting the role of cultural knowledge, skills, and resources in perpetuating educational inequities. Bourdieu's lens allowed for an exploration of how cultural capital, including language proficiency, familiarity with academic discourse, and exposure to cultural practices, can impact academic success. By interpreting these theories for my research, it laid a solid foundation for comprehending and addressing gender inequities in education.

Results

Niger

Niger has the lowest girls' enrollment, retention, and school completion rates. Table 2 highlights the disparities in relation to location. One of the reasons behind this is that rural government schools are extremely poor in quality and resources. Many of the girls who do graduate from primary school in rural areas, graduate without learning how to read. For many parents living in rural areas, the opportunity cost of losing their daughter's labor is not worth the poor learning outcomes. (World Bank Document, 2019).

Table 2. Educational Levels Among Girls in Niger

Location	No Level	Primary Incomplete	Primary Complete	Secondary Incomplete	Secondary Complete	Superior
Combined	66	11	6	15	1	<1
Urban	33	12	8	39	3	5
Rural	75	11	5	9	<1	<1

There are other factors besides location that effects their level of education including social beliefs, norms, and practices (UNICEF, 2022). There is a major correlation between child marriage and education (DHS, 2021). For women 20-24, 81% are married without an education. In Niger, there is not a specific minimal age when a girl must be married or that she must be married at a specific age. However, when the child's mother notices that she is menstruating and has developed breasts, usually is an indicator that the parents decide she is ready to be married (World Bank Document, 2019).

Figure 2: Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in Niger

Figure two shows the literacy rate among men and women in Niger from 2001- 2021. Here it can be seen that women are lagging behind men. Other obstacles that girls and women

face in relation to education include poor learning outcomes, failure in primary school completion exams, lack of nearby schools, forced withdrawal of married adolescents, never enrolling, and demands on first daughters (WBD, 2019). According to the Demographic Health Surveys, education is one of the five domain of impacts causing gender inequity in Niger along with fertility, health and nutrition, labor and earnings, decision making, and violence, but it is a major factor when assessing the future of the country.

Haiti

Over 80% of the schools in Haiti are privately owned by local communities, NGOs, religious organizations, and for-profit companies. These schools require all students to pay fees for the operation of the school (The LEVE Project, 2023). The other 20% of schools are usually outside, houses, or in churches. There is a 57% enrollment rate for children attending primary school (6-14) and 20% enrollment rate for young adults attending secondary school (15-18), which is shown by Figure 3.

Figure 3: Education Enrollment in Haiti

Education Enrollment in Haiti

Some of the educational challenges in Haiti have been exacerbated by the president's assassination in 2021 and the vulnerability to earthquakes (The LEVE Project, 2023). Haiti's

education budget is 10%, public school teachers do not have a salary, and 78% of the population live on less than \$2 USD a day.

Here is a breakdown of the costs that private students pay (converted to USD):

- School Fees for the year - average \$200
- Textbooks - \$120
- Required Uniform - \$50
- School Shoes - \$20
- School Supplies - \$30
- **Total - \$420**

In Haiti, women have poor and limited access to maternal and reproductive healthcare (DHS, 2019). In Haiti, many men and women believe that wife beating is justified. So many women face psychological, sexual, and emotional violence (World Bank, 2023). Women are more likely to be unemployed. In rural and urban areas, boys have higher net attendance rates than girls in primary school, and adult men have consistently remained significantly more likely to have attended or completed secondary and tertiary education (World Bank, 2023).

Figure 4: Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in Haiti

Adult female literacy rate in Haiti is slightly lower than male literacy rate, as shown by

Figure 4. However, this data still shows evidence of gender inequity caused by the traditional

gender roles that limit educational opportunities for women. When there are issues of economic constraints, parents are much more likely to send their sons to school compared to their daughters (World Bank, 2023).

Central African Republic

Central African Republic (CAR) is described as one of the toughest places to live in the world as a child (Ayoola, 2023). The Anti-balaka is an alliance of militia groups originated in the CAR in 2013 as a response to the rise of Michel Djotodia. The Anti-balaka, composed of primarily Christians, emerged in response of the Seleka rebels who were aggrieved by years of impoverishment, insecurity, and weak social services, composed of primarily Muslims. The primary goal when starting the Anti-balaka was to protect the group, but it quickly led to attacks and violence.

Figure 5. Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in Central African Republic

Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in Central African Republic (15+)

Fighters occupy schools and expose students and teachers to risk. They have damaged and destroyed schools, which are already of poor quality and insufficient amount for students, as they occupy schools and burn the desks and chairs for cooking fuel (Human Rights Watch,

Figure 7: Percentage of Children of Secondary School Ages 12-18 Out of School in Central African Republic

PERCENTAGE OF CHILDREN OF SECONDARY SCHOOL AGES 12-18 OUT OF SCHOOL IN CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC

Approximately 31% of child marriages involves partners who are 0-4 years older, 35% involve partners who are 5-9 years older, and 25% involve partners who are 10+ years older (OCHA, 2023). As girls get married young, they are also forced into early pregnancy and domestic violence (Ayoola, 2023). Other gender-based violence that occurs include psychological and psychological violence, rape, and female genital mutilation which are reinforced by socio-cultural norms disadvantaging girls and women (OCHA, 2023).

India

Illiterate women in India have high levels of fertility, mortality, low earning potential, and little autonomy within the household (Census, 2021). Many women and girls in India do not enjoy many of their rights because of patriarchal views, norms, traditions, and structures (UNICEF, 2022). As seen by Figure 8, it can be seen the substantial difference among genders who have not received schooling and by Figure 9, where women are trailing behind when comparing literacy rates among men and women. Women are taught to be submissive to men and

often lack awareness when it comes to achieving gender equity. Men and boys are seen as dominant and powerful and experience freedom, whereas women and girls experience many limitations as they cannot make individual decisions regarding their work, marriage, education, and social relationships (UNICEF, 2022).

“The term Paraya dhan is often used to describe girls in India. The term refers to the view in society that girls are a liability. Paraya means “not one’s own,” while dhan translates to property and wealth, reflecting the cultural belief that girls are meant to be transferred from the ownership of their father to that of their husband when they marry” (Cook, 2020).

Figure 8: Percentage of People in India with No Schooling

In India, more than 23 million girls drop out each year because of the lack of necessary menstrual products and hygiene education (Cook, 2020). One out of five girls miss school during their period, 45% of girls who do not attend school reported concentration problems while menstruating, 36% of girls did not attend school because they were scared of staining or smelling in class, and 80+% of girls were using cloths and lacked access to sanitary pads or tampons

(Cook, 2020). Another reason contributing to women and girls lack of education is child labor. According to the International Labor Organization, India has one of the highest numbers of child laborers in the world, with approximately 10.1 million children engaged in such work. (ILO, 2019). Despite the creating of the Child Labor Act of 1986 which prohibited children under the age of 14 from working, there are millions of children, mostly girls, who are involved in domestic and agriculture work (Cook, 2020). The government can monitor factories and business, but they cannot monitor households, leading to large numbers of girls and young women who are domestic laborers.

Figure 9. Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in India

Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in India (15+)

Afghanistan

According to the newspaper Hasht-e-Subh, as of last December Afghanistan decided to change their curriculum and mandated for “removing images of all living beings, propagating jihad, justifying violence, bloodshed and destruction, prohibiting any advocacy for democracy and human rights, opposition to women’s education and freedom, propagating the Taliban’s narrative of history, focusing on the Islamic world and ignoring the non-Islamic world,

especially the West” (O’Donnell, 2023). School in Afghanistan is mostly Kalashnikovs, suicide bombings, and the Quran (O’Donnell, 2023). Society can be indoctrinated through education, and that is precisely what Afghanistan is doing.

While examining the literacy rates in Afghanistan, as shown in figure 10, it is evident that women face significant barriers in accessing education compared to men. The Taliban is a radical Islamist group that emerged in Afghanistan, imposing strict Islamic law, and gaining notoriety for its harsh treatment of women and human rights violations.

Figure 10. Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in Afghanistan

During 1996 through 2001, the Taliban denied women and girls education (OHCHR, 2023). Between 2001 and 2018, Afghanistan saw a tenfold increase in enrollment at all levels, beginning with approximately 1 million students in 2001 to approximately 10 million students in 2018 (UNESCO, 2023). In 2018 the number of girls in primary schools increased from almost zero in 2001 to 2.5 million in 2018. By 2018 one out of three women were enrolled in universities and four out of ten students in primary education were girls (UNESCO, 2023).

However, this changed after the Taliban's rise to power in 2021. One of their first acts was implementing a strict interpretation of Islamic law, which included the prohibition of girls and women from attending school and university (Basitkey, 2023). The reasoning behind this, was through the Islamic law, the Taliban believed that education was not necessary and not appropriate for girls and women (Basitkey, 2023). In 2023, schools reopened, but girls cannot go to school beyond 6th grade (Basitkey, 2023). Afghanistan is the only country that forbids girls and young women from attending secondary school and places of higher education. As of now, there is no intention for allowing older girls to go to school. Currently, women are banned from public places such as parks and most forms of employment and 80% (2.5 million) of Afghan girls and young women are not in school (UNESCO, 2023).

Ecuador

Although education is provided at no cost in Ecuador, children encounter various obstacles in obtaining education, including financial constraints preventing the purchase of school attire and books, limited physical accessibility to educational facilities and instructors, insufficient educational infrastructure, and unreliable public transportation systems, which, combined with a scarcity of schools in rural and Indigenous regions, result in longer commutes, ultimately reducing the likelihood of school attendance among children residing in these areas (US Department of Labor, 2020).

Latin America and the Caribbean had the world's longest COVID- related school shutdowns, with 71% of school weeks closed between March 2020 through November 2021 (Sweigart, 2021). As shown by Table 3, Ecuador demonstrates a significant challenge in education, with 63% of 10-year-olds below the proficient reading level in 2019, a dropout rate of 4.8% in 2020, and only 14% of students receiving face-to-face classes in 2021. The transition to

remote online learning led to many school dropouts because students did not have access to the Internet, mobile devices, laptops, or other electronic equipment. During the 2020-2021 school year, there were approximately 100,000 children in Ecuador that did not register for school because they lacked access to digital devices needed for schooling (Cordeiro, 2022).

Table 3. Educational Performance Indicators by Country (2019-2021)

Countries	Percentage of 10-year-olds below proficient reading level in 2019	Percentage of dropout rate in 2020	Percentage of students receiving face-to-face classes in 2021
Argentina	54%	2.8%	94%
Costa Rica	33%	4.3%	100%
Bolivia	49%	3.4%	73%
Panama	67%	4.5%	39%
Ecuador	63%	4.8%	14%

As illustrated by Figure 11, while literacy rates between men and women in Ecuador are comparable, women face slightly more challenges, such as limited access to educational resources, opportunities, and school-related sexual violence, despite their relatively similar literacy levels. In Ecuador, the problem of sexual violence within educational settings has persisted for a significant period, and since 2014, cases have been on the rise. Incidents of sexual violence have been reported across various school levels, from preschool to primary and secondary school, involving janitors, bus drivers, school personnel, and teachers, affecting students in both public and private educational institutions, including those with disabilities (Cordeiro, 2022).

Government data revealed that between 2014 and 2020, there were 4,221 reported cases of school-related sexual violence in Ecuador (Human Rights Watch, 2020). In 2020, the Inter-American Court of Human Rights addressed its first-ever school related sexual violence claim, *Paola Guzmán v Ecuador*, concerning a 14-year-old student subjected to ongoing rape for a year.

Despite the student's complaints to the school, protective measures were not implemented, tragically resulting in the student taking her own life (Cordeiro, 2022).

Figure 11. Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in Ecuador

Literacy Rate Among Men and Women in Ecuador (15+)

Ecuador ranks third in the South American region for adolescent pregnancy rates, significantly affecting girl's education rates. Between 2015 and 2020, the adolescent birth rate for girls aged 15 to 19 was 64% (UNICEF, 2021). Out of every 100 live births in the country, 49.3 were attributed to adolescent mothers, with the past decade witnessing a 78% rise in births among girls aged 10 to 14 and an 11% increase among girls aged 15 to 19 (Benalcazar, 2019).

Guatemala

Gender disparities are prevalent regarding educational access and opportunities, particularly in rural and indigenous communities. Guatemala has a patriarchal society. In relation to education, there are cultural norms that prioritize boys' education, and girls are more likely to dropout due to economic hardships, societal pressures, early marriage, and adolescent pregnancy (Asturias, 2023). In 2022, 23,000 girls were out of school in the Sololá department in Guatemala, In Guatemala, approximately one out of every three girls graduate from 6th grade (Asturias,

2023). As highlighted by Tables 4 and 5, Guatemala exhibits a notable gender disparity in education, with men demonstrating a higher likelihood of attaining more years of schooling compared to women.

Table 4. Distribution of Male Population Level by the Highest Level of Education Completed (2017)

Age	No education	Incomplete Primary	Primary Complete	Secondary Incomplete	Secondary Complete	Higher Education	Median School Years
15-19	2%	17%	22.9%	53.1%	4.3%	0.7%	6.8
20-24	4.1%	19.1%	16.9%	33.5%	17.5%	8.9%	8.2
25-29	7.6%	23.4%	18.7%	23.2%	15.3%	11.8%	6.1
30-34	10.1%	28.6%	18.6%	21.5%	11.0%	10.2%	5.6
35-39	13.1%	31.1%	18.3%	18.8%	9.4%	9.3%	5.3
40-44	14.0%	34.0%	21.8%	13.8%	7.1%	9.4%	5.1

Table 5. Distribution of Female Population Level by the Highest Level of Education Completed (2017)

Age	No education	Incomplete Primary	Primary Complete	Secondary Incomplete	Secondary Complete	Higher Education	Median School Years
15-19	3.3%	21.1%	23.0%	46.7%	4.9%	1.1%	6.4
20-24	6.9%	23.9%	17.5%	26.3%	16.0%	9.4%	6.7
25-29	13.1%	29.2%	14.7%	18.9%	13.0%	11.0%	5.5
30-34	19.6%	31.5%	16.6%	15.6%	8.9%	7.8%	4.6
35-39	23.3%	35.7%	14.4%	12.7%	7.7%	6.3%	2.9
40-44	25.0%	35.7%	15.8%	11.1%	5.9%	6.5%	2.7

In Guatemala, the issue of inadequate teacher training has posed a significant challenge to the quality of education. The majority of instructors in Guatemalan primary schools have only completed high school-level education, limiting their exposure to best practices in teaching. Many educators are unfamiliar with the subjects, techniques, and methods that could enable them to adapt and improve their teaching style, further exacerbating the difficulties in providing a high-quality education (Fajkus, 2022).

Another significant challenge prevalent to Guatemala's ability to have high quality education is the scarcity of essential resources, particularly age-appropriate Spanish-language

books. There is a lack of necessary materials, leaving students and teachers with a few copies of outdated textbooks or scraps of newspapers as reading materials, so students have little opportunities to read independently and explore their interests (Fajkus, 2022).

Access to quality education remains even more difficult for girls, particularly those belonging to Indigenous communities in rural areas and those facing poverty. The pandemic has disrupted an already fragile education system and exacerbated the economic crisis. As families grapple with financial challenges, many parents have chosen to withdraw their children from school, with girls disproportionately affected as the first to be removed from educational settings (Asturias, 2023).

70% of children attend school without acquiring fundamental reading and writing competencies. Approximately about 40% of sixth graders attain the expected performance levels in reading, underscoring the educational disparities prevalent in Guatemala. The majority of Guatemalan adolescents do not progress to high school, contributing to a 41% rate of out-of-school teenagers nationwide. In the western highlands, predominantly inhabited by indigenous communities, this rate further escalates to 61%, emphasizing the pronounced gender and cultural inequities embedded within the educational system (Fajkus, 2022).

China

Ancient China experienced a long period of patriarchal society, emphasizing "Ignorance is a woman's virtue", when women basically did not receive education, thus most are illiterate (Lu and Du, 2022, p. 1). In the 19th century, after the 1911 Revolution, as connections between East and West strengthened, more women gained education in schools or missionary girls' schools. There became significant progress in education for girls and women in China. This can be contributed to the legal recognition of women's right to education, evolving social concepts,

and a resounding demand for equal education rights. However, social unrest and unequal development hindered the advancement of women's education during this time. By 1949, the female illiteracy rate had reached 90% (Lu and Du, 2022, p. 2). Notably, in the past four decades of reform and development, women's education, particularly in higher education, has flourished, culminating in a state where Chinese women now enjoy equal rights with men in education, as illustrated by Figures 12 and 13.

Figure 12. Female Illiteracy Rate in China

The progress in female education is evidenced by key indicators such as the female illiteracy rate, girls' enrollment rate, the number of girls in school, and the average duration of female education. By 1990, the illiteracy rate among Chinese women had dropped to 32%, primarily attributed to the significant increase in girls' school enrollment rates since 1949 (Lu and Du, 2022, p. 2). There was a sharp rise in the proportion of female postgraduate students, from 26% in 1993 to 54.98% in 2020. As of recently, girls are beginning to equal boys in education in terms of the number of enrollments, dominating across academic fields, and organizations are making a tangible difference, resulting in the progress in China's education that has led to many successful women (Merchant, 2018).

Introduced in 2011, the China National Program for Women's Development (2011-2020), known as the NPA for Women, aimed to protect women's rights, promote women's development, and advance equity between men and women. Since its implementation there became increased opportunities for women to access higher education. Financial aid has been given to low-income female students and female students with disabilities, ensuring equitable access to education for women (NBS, 2021).

Figure 13. Enrollment Rate of Girls of School Age in China

However, in rural western China, the average duration of schooling for women remains at 7.44 years, highlighting the persisting preference for boys and the consequent neglect of female education in these regions. Yet, in urban areas, particularly in major cities, this disparity has significantly diminished, with socioeconomic development and increased parental education levels poised to address this issue in the foreseeable future. Another issue that appears in China is families giving preference to boys based on the belief that boys and men have a better understanding of education and are more respected than educating girls within society.

Additionally, some families believe that women do not have to be educated and hold the idea that women can live good lives by marrying wealthy and well-educated men (Li, 2021, p. 907).

United States

In 1803, Bradford Academy in Massachusetts marked a significant milestone as the first higher educational institution to admit women. Later, in 1831, Mississippi College awarded the first degree to a woman, followed by the University of Iowa in 1855, which became the first co-ed public university. In 1922 Lorna Hodgkinson became the first woman to receive a Ph.D. Despite these advancements, there was resistance to the admission of women into Ivy League universities, as evidenced by the demeaning sentiments expressed in the early 20th century.

“For God's sake, for Dartmouth's sake, and for everyone's sake, keep the damned women out.” “What is all this nonsense about admitting women to Princeton? A good old-fashioned whore-house would be considerably more efficient, and much, much cheaper.” Gentlemen — let's face it — charming as women are — they get to be a drag if you are forced to associate with them each and every day," a Yale alum wrote (Carlton, 2023).

Eventually, Princeton and Yale began admitting women in 1969, with Brown University following in 1971 and Dartmouth in 1972 (Carlton, 2023). Title IX was passed in 1972 and prohibits discrimination on the basis of sex in any educational program or any other education program that receives funding from the government, which serves as a crucial tool for promoting and fostering gender equity in education.

There has been a significant shift in gender inequity over the last five decades, commonly known as a "gender revolution." During this period there was a rise in women's participation in the workforce, with employment becoming customary even for mothers with young children. Additionally, the availability of birth control expanded considerably. There was a substantial

increase in the number of women attaining bachelor's or doctoral degrees, particularly in fields traditionally dominated by men, such as management, accounting, and STEM fields (England et al., 2020, p.6990).

Recently, more women began to take on professional and managerial roles that were previously predominantly occupied by men, leading to a decline in occupational segregation. The gender pay gap also saw a significant decrease post-1980, accompanied by a shift towards more egalitarian attitudes regarding gender roles. However, despite these positive developments, challenges persist in addressing gender bias within the education sector. As of 2019, women comprised the majority of the college-educated workforce, yet men with bachelor's degrees continued to earn approximately \$26,000 more annually than their female counterparts (Wang and Parker, 2021).

Canada

In 1862, Canada marked a significant milestone as the first university to allow female students to enroll. In 1901, women comprised only 13.4% of the paid labor force and faced the legal requirement to resign upon marriage. Later, the employment landscape slowly evolved, with a woman being hired as a professor in 1912, and the female labor force increasing to 15.4% by 1921.

The progress continued with the passage of the Canadian Human Rights Act in 1941, marking a pivotal moment in the advancement of women's rights. The 1980s witnessed notable milestones, such as women surpassing the number of men on campus in 1981, as shown in Figure 14, and the modification of rape laws and the CHRA in 1983 and 1984, respectively. Additionally, the Canadian constitution was amended in 1984, reflecting a deeper commitment to equality and inclusivity.

Figure 14. Students Enrolled in Postsecondary Institutions in Canada from 1960 to 2021

The journey towards gender equity gained momentum, and by 1995, women comprised nearly half of the labor force. This positive trend continued, and in 2009, the labor market witnessed a significant rise in female participation, indicating the ongoing progress in women's empowerment and equality in Canada. One of the goals the Government of Canada has regarding education and skills development is to have equal opportunities and diversified paths. This goal matters to the government because they believe each individual should be empowered to make educational choices aligned with their personal interests, talents, and economic goals, regardless of gender. In addition, educating both genders contribute to the economy by promoting diverse skill sets, adaptability, and a workforce that supports Canada's competitiveness and prosperity (Government of Canada, 2023).

The Netherlands

In the Netherlands, women continue to face significant underrepresentation in politics. Furthermore, they have limited economic opportunities compared to men and are at a higher risk of experiencing violence, which is often based off discrimination and women's subordinate

position. However, the Netherlands is working to strengthen the position of women and girls (Government of the Netherlands, 2023).

The core issues which the Netherlands focuses on include the implementation of UN Resolution 1325, focusing on women's role in peace and security. Efforts are also directed towards combatting violence against women, preventing child marriages, promoting women's participation in politics and the economy, and striving for gender equality between men and women. The Netherlands is actively engaged in promoting equal rights for women and girls globally (Government of the Netherlands, 2023).

The Netherlands demonstrates its dedication to enhancing women's rights and achieving gender equity through active participation in international conventions, resolutions, and agreements. One example is the biennial UN resolution co-launched by the Netherlands and France, advocating for increased global attention and action to address violence against women (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2020).

The Netherlands is consistently rated as number one for happiness due to their high quality of life, great health system, good work/ life balance, safety and security, and multicultural society (Knotman, 2023). Society in the Netherlands has made children feel less pressured to excel in school. For example, in the Netherlands, education is not solely about excellent grades and prestigious institutions. It is regarded as the pathway to a child's overall well-being and individual growth (Acosta, 2019).

Finland

Finland's key priorities include using education as a means to reduce social inequity, ensuring that all students have access to free school meals, facilitating easy access to healthcare, providing psychological counseling, and offering personalized guidance to students (Colagrossi,

2018). In Finland, the education system is characterized by several key features. Education is universally accessible and publicly funded, ensuring that all students have equal access to high-quality education. A strong focus is placed on student well-being, with an emphasis on physical activity, outdoor time, and mental health, exemplified by longer recess periods compared to other countries, such as 75 minutes in Finland compared to 25 minutes in the United States (Rastogi, 2023).

The presence of small class sizes and highly trained teachers fosters a supportive learning environment. The curriculum takes a holistic approach, nurturing creativity, critical thinking, and collaboration skills. Students are actively engaged in their learning and personal development. Equity is a fundamental principle, reflected in the inclusive educational practices that contribute to the country's social and economic progress. Schools ensure access to meals, healthcare, counseling, and even transportation services if required. Additionally, the Finnish education system is recognized for its innovative methods, utilizing modern pedagogical techniques and technology to enhance the overall learning experience for students (Rastogi, 2023).

The Finnish education system further distinguishes itself through the absence of standardized testing, with the exception of one optional exam (Aedo et al., 2017). Teachers are highly regarded and are required to hold master's degrees. They adapt their teaching methods to address the specific needs of individual students, with no separate classrooms for special education or accelerated learners. Additionally, all schools receive full state funding, eliminating the presence of private institutions. The educational culture does not foster competition, instead emphasizing cooperation and collaboration. The high school graduation rate in Finland stands at 93%, surpassing rates in both Canada (78%) and the United States (75%), and has a significant amount of students who further their education.

Thematic Review

Gender inequity in education remains a persistent and concerning issue worldwide, with various countries grappling with multifaceted challenges that restrict girl's and women's access to quality education. In Niger, girls' educational attainment is significantly affected by location, social beliefs, and child marriage practices. Haiti struggles with financial barriers and cultural norms that limit girls' access to education, exacerbated by social and gender-based violence. Central African Republic faces significant challenges due to political instability, conflicts, and deeply ingrained gender-based discrimination, leading to limited educational opportunities for girls. India struggles with societal constraints and cultural beliefs that disproportionality effect girls' education, along with issues related to menstrual hygiene and child labor.

Afghanistan has experienced significant setbacks in girls' education due to the repressive policies of the Taliban, leading to a decline in educational opportunities for women. Ecuador faces challenges related to sexual violence within educational settings and high rates of adolescent pregnancy, significantly impacting girls' education. Guatemala struggles with cultural biases and economic hardships, particularly in rural and indigenous communities, leading to gender disparities in educational access and opportunities.

China has made significant progress in women's education over the years, but historical gender norms and disparities in rural areas continue to affect girls' education. The United States and Canada have made substantial strides in addressing gender discrimination in education, although disparities persist in terms of workforce participation and the gender pay gap. The Netherlands and Finland have implemented various policies and initiatives to promote gender equity in education, with an emphasis on social well-being, inclusive practices, and equitable access to educational resources for all students.

Across the different countries researched, there are some specific country related elements when observing gender inequity in education. However, there are many common themes regarding gender inequity in education that were observed. The purposes of this thematic review are to identify and explore common themes, patterns, and trends across the evaluated countries.

Socio-Cultural Barriers

Across the examined countries, socio-cultural factors have been found to significantly contribute to gender inequity in education. Societal beliefs, norms, and practices, including patriarchal attitudes, limited roles for women, and traditional views on gender roles, have hindered the educational opportunities for girls and women. These attitudes often lead to early marriages, limited autonomy for girls and women, and reinforced gender-based violence.

Economic Constraints

Economic challenges have been a key barrier to accessing education for girls in various situations. In countries such as Haiti, Ecuador, and Guatemala, financial constraints have led to difficulties in affording school fees, uniforms, and necessary educational materials. Additionally, in India, the prevalence of child labor has been a significant obstacle for girls' education, as many are forced into domestic and agricultural work instead of attending school.

Quality of Education

Several countries, including Niger, Haiti, and the Central African Republic, have faced significant challenges in providing quality education, particularly in rural areas. Inadequate resources, poor infrastructure, and lack of trained teachers have led to substandard educational experiences for girls, resulting in lower literacy rates and limited learning outcomes compared to their male counterparts.

Political and Social Instability

In conflict-affected regions such as Afghanistan and the Central African Republic, political and social instability have had a detrimental impact on girls' education. Militarization of schools, destruction of educational facilities, and increased risks of violence and insecurity have led to a significant decrease in educational opportunities for girls and young women, often forcing them out of school and limiting their access to education.

Legal Frameworks

In several countries, including India and Afghanistan, legal frameworks and cultural norms have perpetuated gender inequity in education. Discriminatory laws and practices, such as early marriage, limited autonomy for women, and gender-based violence, have further reinforced existing gender disparities in education.

Health and Well-being

Issues related to health and well-being, including limited access to reproductive healthcare, high rates of adolescent pregnancy, and the lack of menstrual hygiene resources, have posed significant challenges for girls' education in countries such as Ecuador, India, and Guatemala. These challenges have often led to girls missing school, experiencing health-related barriers, and facing stigma and discrimination, affecting their educational outcomes.

Conclusion and Call to Action

Educating women is crucial, for not only the woman herself, but for the overall society. As said by Carol Bellamy, former director of the Peace Corps of the United States and former New York State Center, "Girls' education is the single best investment that any society can make." By giving girls and young women, high quality education, they become empowered and have improved health and well-being. This benefits far more than the individual level, educating

women has generational outcomes as they contribute to the economic development, have fewer children, are given informed choices about family growth, and are more likely to have well-nourished offspring with higher survival rates (United Nations, 2023).

Finland's education system has gained worldwide recognition for its effectiveness and focus on equity. This country is a great example of promoting gender equity in education, and it would be beneficial if all countries were able to have an educational system similar to Finland's. Finland's advantageous educational factors can be characterized by equal access to education, gender-neutral curriculum, teacher training and support, emphasis on individual learning and achievement, and a supportive school environment.

Some recommendations to achieve gender equity in education include ensuring that teachers, administrators, parents, community leaders, and employers are fully aligned and coordinated. This involves providing girls and women with educational opportunities that integrate awareness in health, nutrition, and physical and emotional well-being. Additionally, initiatives should be designed to be inclusive of boys and men. Other strategies include increasing opportunities for girls' leadership training, improving knowledge and awareness of harmful practices and human rights abuses, and imparting essential life skills (Basic Education Coalition, 2017).

Policies should focus on banning harmful practices like female genital mutilization, child marriage, gender-based violence, and child trafficking. Policies should also aim to prohibit any and all forms of discrimination based on gender in educational institutions. Additionally, they should enhance access to education such as providing transportation, sanitary facilities with menstrual products, and any other necessary resources they may need, and allocate sufficient

resources to promote and support all children's education at all levels, with initiatives aimed at addressing girl's specific needs in education.

Limitations and Future Research

One limitation of this study was the use of Google Translate during the literature review for non-English publications, specifically the Demographic and Health Surveys, which used data in French and Spanish to represent the household surveys.

While this study delves into gender inequities across twelve diverse countries, there is potential for a more extensive global comparative analysis. Future research could include additional countries to broaden the scope, allowing for a comprehensive examination of regional patterns and variations in gender disparities.

It might be appropriate to take an ethnographic approach to deepen the understanding of the underlying reasonings of gender inequity in educational access. Some examples could be performing interviews from people living in or from these countries or observing people both inside and outside educational facilities. Talking to people directly from these countries or even visiting these countries might support my data or reveal new ideas that influence gender inequity in education.

I believe in starting small and being patient. It might not be feasible for developing countries to open public education for people of all ages at the snap of a finger. However, if these countries started with providing access to sanitary products or simply raising the minimum age to 18 in order to marry, they might be on track to forming public educational systems for all genders and ages. Evaluating the impact of specific policies, programs, or initiatives implemented in these countries or others can provide evidence-based insights into what works and why, informing the development of more effective interventions.

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